

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN INCREASING ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AMONG MSU-SULU SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL GRADE 12 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Social media is well documented globally and has become an integral part of modern life as a means of connecting, sharing, and learning. However, there is a lack of research specifically focused on how social media impact student engagement in environmental sustainability. Using checklist survey questionnaire, the study aims to investigate the level of social media usage and environmental awareness among students, identify social media platforms that are most effective for promoting environmental awareness among students, and examine the relationships between the student's social media usage and their environmental awareness. Employing quantitative correlations. The researchers used convenient sampling method in choosing the respondents and utilized checklist survey questionnaire in gathering the data from 130 respondents, we then analyzed the data using Spearman rho correlational analysis and Descriptive frequency analysis. The results showed that the level of social media usage among students is moderate, with a combined total of 29.2% of students spend 1 to 2 hours on social media, the level of environmental awareness among students is also moderate, with 40% of students rated their environmental awareness as 3/5 and the most effective platform for environmental awareness are Facebook (61.5%), TikTok (30%) and YouTube (23.8%). The findings also showed that there is a weak positive correlation between social media usage and environmental awareness among students ($r = .177$, $p = 0.044$, 2-tailed $< p 0.05$). Social media usage among students can significantly influence their environmental awareness,

However, other factors beyond social media are likely to contribute to environmental awareness.

Keywords: *Social media, Environmental awareness, Environmental education, Sustainability, Students.*

INTRODUCTION

With billions of users worldwide, social media has become an integral part of modern life as a means of connecting, sharing, and learning. Since many people and groups have raised awareness of environmental and social issues on social media sites like Facebook, Tiktok, Youtube, Instagram, and Twitter, it has also proven to be a useful tool for promoting sustainability. The platforms are well suited for promoting sustainability because of certain qualities. For instance, hashtags categorize and make postings easier to find, allowing interested individuals to quickly locate and begin interacting with sustainability related information (Kaur & Chahal, 2018).

Moreover, social media serves as a tool to promote awareness regarding various and current environmental issues such as climate change, pollution, and deforestation in a much faster way and to a large audience within a very short span of time. The importance of environmental education in determining the value of social media can be seen through the interaction between environmental educators and students (Mallick & Bajpai, 2019). These interactions not only enhance the learning experience but also help in disseminating crucial environmental information to a broader audience, thereby increasing overall environmental awareness.

Numerous studies show that social media platforms have strong potential as a tool for fostering engagement in environmental action, particularly by increasing awareness, promoting collaboration, and motivating real-world environmental activities.

Despite this potential of social media, there is a lack of research specifically focused on how social media impacts student engagement in environmental action within senior high schools in the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao. Understanding how social media can enhance environmental awareness and mobilize students to act in their local communities is vital. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap.

The respondents of this study will only include grade 12 students at Mindanao State University Sulu Senior High Schools and will not include other students from different departments or schools.

This study aims to identify the role of social media in increasing environmental awareness among Mindanao State University Sulu Senior High School grade 12 students. Specifically, the study aims to investigate the level of social media usage and environmental awareness among students, identify social media platforms that are most effective for promoting environmental awareness among students, and examine the

relationships between the student's social media usage and their environmental awareness.

Through this research, the researcher seeks to provide insights into the potential of social media as a catalyst for environmental advocacy within educational settings, promote student engagement in environmental activities, inform policy and program development, and contribute to the growing body of knowledge on digital engagement in environmental education.

The researcher believes that the findings will contribute to the existing body of knowledge, provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of social media in increasing environmental awareness and engagement of students, which can lead to better understanding of environmental issues, foster engagement, and solve environmental problems. Additionally, the researcher believe that the findings will benefit educators and administrators at MSU-Sulu by enhancing curriculum and outreach programs using social media. Environmental organizations and NGOs can use the insights to improve communication strategies and outreach programs. Local governments and policymakers can use from the findings to formulate better environmental policies and programs. The research community will benefit the growing body of research on social media's impact on environmental awareness and engagement. The findings will also contribute to the community at large, encouraging other schools, organizations, and the community to recognize the potential of social media for environmental involvement among young people.

Social media usage and Environmental issue awareness among Students

Social media has become very popular amongst people because it offers entertainment and information, including a wide range of web technologies like blogs, wikis, and online social networks and virtual networks. It plays a huge role in the lives of children and teenagers, including students (Tkáčová et al., 2021). Additionally, the reason behind such rapid growth is that teenagers and university students are using social media applications to have access all over the world. Social media sites like Facebook and Twitter are becoming the craze in our society for everyone these days (Kim et al., 2018).

Furthermore, social media has been proven to help students avoid misinformation about environmental issues and raises their awareness of the need for a frugal attitude toward nature and the environmentally friendly use of natural resources. This is particularly important in an era where environmental sustainability is a global concern. By providing accurate information and promoting sustainable practices, social media can play a crucial role in shaping the environmental attitudes and behaviors of young people (Lovochkina et al., 2023). Additionally, social media has played a significant role in raising public awareness of environmental issues, expanding the public's reach, and empowering users to influence changes in the environmental sector on a variety of issues, including pollution and climate change (Sharma et al., 2024). Moreover, since social media expands the public's reach and enables users to impact changes in the environmental sector on various issues, including the transition to renewable energy sources and climate

change dialogues, this can highlight the potential of social media to facilitate global conversations about environmental issues and promote collective action (Asha et al. 2024).

Furthermore, exposure to environmental information on social media platforms has been shown to positively affect individuals' intentions to participate in pro-environmental behaviors. For instance, a study by Meng et al. (2023) found that exposure to environmental information on Chinese social media platforms like WeChat significantly increased young adults' intentions to engage in pro-environmental actions. This suggests that social media can be an effective tool for promoting environmental awareness and encouraging sustainable behaviors.

Social media provides a space for environmental activists and organizations to share information, mobilize support, and advocate for policy changes. This has led to increased public participation in environmental campaigns and a greater sense of community among those concerned about environmental issues. For example, social media can be used to organize and promote events such as climate strikes or environmental protests, which can raise awareness and put pressure on policymakers to take action.

However, social media usage among students has been linked to their social anxiety, well-being and academic performance. A study by Sun (2023) found that mindfulness-based mobile apps can reduce anxiety and enhance well-being among students. This suggests that social media can have both positive and negative effects on students' mental health, depending on how it is used.

Likewise, the effect of social media on students' emotional well-being has been extensively studied. Chen & Xiao (2022) reviewed the potential effects of social media on students' stress, anxiety, and depression, highlighting both positive and negative impacts. This underscores the need for students to use social media mindfully and for educators to provide guidance on healthy social media use.

Moreover, social media usage has been associated with academic performance. Zhang et al. (2024) found that social media use positively correlates with academic performance when moderated by mental well-being, family bonding, and collaborative learning. This suggests that social media can be a valuable tool for academic support, provided that it is used in a balanced and mindful way.

Additionally, a study by Nagata et al. (2024) found that excessive screen time on social media increases the likelihood of early substance use among adolescents, emphasizing the need for media literacy and monitoring screen habits. This highlights the potential risks associated with excessive social media use and the importance of promoting healthy screen habits among students.

Social media has proven to be effective as a powerful tool for spreading environmental information and fostering a culture of sustainability among students and

the broader public. Its ability to connect individuals and amplify voices makes it an essential component in the fight against environmental challenges. However, it is important for students to use social media mindfully, because other studies have also proven that excessive social media usage can cause anxiety and affect student well-being and academic performance.

Effectiveness of Social media platforms in Raising awareness

Global media and social media have fueled the development of independent environmental activists, providing platforms for environmental campaigns, mobilizing support, organizing events, and creating online petitions. These platforms expand the public's reach and enable users to impact changes in the environmental sector on various issues, including the transition to renewable energy sources and ongoing dialogues about climate change (Sharma et al., 2024).

Moreover, while traditional media was the most important source for news and information regarding environmental problems such as climate change and air pollution, today it has been overtaken by the internet (Luo et al., 2020).

Additionally, social media has the potential to be a social learning environment, even though its usage for environmental awareness is somewhat limited. To encourage this use, Studies suggests open online communication and capacity building. By fostering an environment where individuals can freely share and discuss environmental issues, social media can become a powerful tool for environmental education and awareness (Waititu, 2021).

Furthermore, social media has become a catalyst for raising environmental awareness, fostering dialogue, and inspiring positive change. Moreover, billions of users worldwide, social media platforms offer a unique opportunity to engage in diverse communities and share compelling narratives about environmental issues (Silva, 2024).

Consequently, social media has been a very significant platform where organizations, climate activists, influencers, scientists, and policymakers of all kinds raise global awareness of climate change and pro-environmental behavior (Balardi, 2023). Furthermore, wide access to social media has also improved environmental governance; research involving Weibo has demonstrated that public pressure from such mass communication networks has turned out to be an increasingly important driver of environmental policy and action (Wang et al., 2023).

Moreover, social media serves as a tool to promote awareness regarding various and current environmental issues in a much faster way and to a large audience within a very short span of time. The importance of environmental education in determining the value of social media can be seen through the interaction between environmental educators and students (Mallick & Bajpai 2019). These interactions not only enhance the learning experience but also help in disseminating crucial environmental information to a broader audience, thereby increasing overall environmental awareness.

Consequently, social media as a catalyst for environmental activism social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and Twitter have proven to be highly effective in promoting environmental causes Puentes (2021). These platforms enable users to share information rapidly, leading to widespread public engagement and action. A notable example is the TikTok videos highlighting environmental issues, such as the red tide in Florida, which sparked significant public participation in cleanup efforts. Additionally, utilizing visual content and storytelling like those can make climate change information more relatable and engaging, thereby enhancing its impact (Mavrodieva et al., 2019).

Furthermore, YouTube is the highest and most significant positive influence on climate change awareness among Latin American users, followed by Instagram, Twitter, and WhatsApp. However, Facebook and LinkedIn have no significant effects; in fact, some exert a negative influence on users about their knowledge of climate change (Gomez & Gomez 2023).

Moreover, Social media could magnify the effects of interpersonal communication on risk perception and further influence pro-environmental behavior (Han et al., 2020) Moreover, applying interpersonal communication strategies (e.g., selfies or images and videos, captions containing first-person pronouns, responses to comments) got the highest degree of engagement in two-way dialogue between content creators and their audience on social media platforms (Martin et al., 2020).

Additionally, the impact of social media campaigns on public action social media campaigns like #TrashTag have demonstrated the potential of digital platforms to inspire grassroots environmental action. These campaigns, often spread through platforms like Instagram and Twitter, have led to global participation in environmental cleanup efforts. Social media has been instrumental in raising awareness, motivating individuals to take tangible steps toward environmental conservation (Rutledge, 2019) and mobilizing young audiences, enabling them to take part in environmental movements and campaigns.

Furthermore, Media and Information Literacy (MIL) plays a key role in helping young people navigate environmental issues and adopt sustainable practices. Social media acts as a vehicle for promoting green skills and fostering sustainable behavior among the youth UNESCO (2023).

In addition, the role of social media was found to be vital in advancing environmental health and awareness. Findings show that social media played a key role in raising awareness to mobilizing support and influencing policymakers. Social networking sites also helped activists frame environmental issues in emotionally engaging ways, strengthening public pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors (Amin, 2024).

The Literatures showed the effectiveness and the significance of social media in increasing environmental awareness among students. And it was found that the most effective social media platforms in spreading environmental awareness are Youtube and Tiktok, Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook due to its visual content and storytelling which makes it more relatable to the users and also, these platforms enable users to share

information rapidly, leading to widespread public engagement and action, making spreading awareness easier.

Research Gaps

The reviewed literature shows that social media has strong potential as a tool for engaging students in environmental action, particularly by increasing awareness, promoting collaboration, and motivating real-world environmental activities. However, there is a need for localized studies, particularly in the Philippine context, to understand how to best utilize social media for environmental education among high school students in rural areas like Sulu. This study will contribute to this gap by investigating the role of social media in increasing environmental issue awareness among students at the Mindanao State University Sulu Senior High School, providing insights into effective strategies and potential challenges specific to the region.

Moreover, Studies show results of various misleading claims in videos related to environmental topics. Also, emphasizing the importance of science education in addressing misleading information is crucial. In addition, the importance of an interdisciplinary approach for addressing environmental issues needs to be reinforced. Additionally, it was also found that digital divide might also pose to be a hindrance in promoting environmental awareness among young people.

Synthesis

Through this Literature review, the researchers deemed social media's role in increasing environmental issue awareness among the students very significant, as other studies proved its importance. Many studies state that since students nowadays are highly exposed to social media, there is a high possibility that they will participate in environmental issue awareness campaigns. Moreover, it was found that visual content and storytelling can make climate change information more relatable and engaging among the students. Furthermore, social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook have emerged as powerful tools for disseminating environmental information, enabling students to engage in global conversations and take collective action. However, misleading information, and digital divide may prove to be a hindrance in spreading environmental issue awareness, and understanding its effectiveness in specific contexts, such as in rural areas like Sulu, Philippines remains unsolved. Literature suggests that localized studies are necessary to explore how social media can be effectively leveraged for environmental education in these regions, where access to digital resources may be limited. Moreover, it was also discovered that too much social media usage may also affect the student's well-being including issues such as social anxiety, depression, and reduced academic performance, therefore it is highly advised by the professionals, that educators, policymakers, and parents should warn, and educate students about the right social media usage. In conclusion, while social media holds significant promises for raising environmental awareness and fostering sustainable behavior among students, its potential is contingent on careful usage.

Research Questions

While social media's role in environmental advocacy is well-documented globally, there is limited research on how these platforms impact senior high school students' engagement in environmental action in the Philippine particularly in specific regions like Sulu. Understanding how social media can enhance environmental awareness and mobilize students to act in their local communities is vital. Therefore, this study will contribute to this gap by identifying the relationship between social media usage and environmental awareness among students at the Mindanao State University Sulu Senior High School. This study aims to answer these specific questions.

1. What is the level of social media usage among MSU-Sulu Senior High School Grade 12 Students?
2. What is the level of Environmental awareness among MSU-Sulu Senior High School Grade 12 Students?
3. Does the frequency of social media usage of students influence the level of their environmental awareness?
4. What specific social media platform is effective in enhancing environmental awareness among MSU-Sulu Senior High School Grade 12 Student?
5. Is there a significant relationship between social media usage and the environmental awareness among MSU-Sulu Senior High School Grade 12 Students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed quantitative approach in this study. The researcher utilized correlational research design to determine the relationship between social media and environmental awareness of students. This design is used to measure the relationship between two variables controlling either of them (McCombes 2019).

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu. The survey questionnaires were given to the selected students inside their own classrooms. The researchers decided this location of implementation due to its convenience to the targeted site to conduct the research, giving the researchers the privilege to easily find their needed information significant to the study that was conducted. This study was carried out in the second semester of the academic year 2024-2025.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were from the STEM 12 and GAS 12 students of the Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School, which has a total of 13 sections and a total student population of 1,022. The researchers only select a total of 130 students as the respondents of this study. 60 students from STEM-12, and 70 students from GAS-12.

The researchers utilized a convenient sampling method of selecting the respondents of this study. The distribution of the respondents using convenient sampling

is presented in the table below. The researcher used only 12.7% of the population of senior high school grade 12 students in MSU-Sulu. Out of 1,022, only 130 students are the chosen respondent of this study. Therefore, the STEM-12 has a total sample of 60 and 70 from the GAS-12.

Table 3.1 Distribution of the respondents according to the total population of grade 12 students in Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School.

Strand and Grade	Population	Percentage	Sample
STEM-12	479	46.9%	60
GAS-12	543	53.1%	70
Total	1,022	100%	130

Instrumentation

The researcher utilized a self-administered checklist questionnaire to gather the necessary data in answering the research problems. The questionnaire was developed by the researcher depending on their prior research, literature review and reading related articles. The instruments undergo a validation process by experts in education to confirm content relevance and clarity. A pilot test was conducted to check the reliability of the instrument. The validation process resulted in a Content Validity Index (CVI) of 0.902, indicating that the items were highly relevant. Meanwhile the reliability analysis produces a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.750, showing acceptable internal consistency across the questionnaire items. The final instrument included multiple choices questions, rating scale, and a five-point Likert scale to effectively gather detailed and meaningful responses from the participants.

Table 3.2 School recommended scale

Scale	Weighted Mean/ Equivalent	Corresponding Remarks
5	4.20- 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.40- 4.19	Agree
3	2.60- 3.39	Neutral
2	1.80- 2.59	Disagree
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

Data Collection

Data collection was planned for over a month with questionnaires distributed during scheduled class sessions. Checklist questionnaires were given to the respondents, and they were guided on the procedure. Participants were given the opportunity to answer all the questions with ease. Data was stored securely, kept in a locked cabinet accessible only to the group.

Statistical Techniques

The following statistical analysis was used to calculate the findings: Spearman's rho correlational analysis, to measure the non-parametric correlation between social media usage and environmental awareness of students; and Descriptive frequencies analysis, to determine how often each response in the questionnaire occur, the researcher also used SPSS software to analyze the data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we systematically present the results and discussion obtained from 130 respondents using checklist survey questionnaire. The data is organized and presented using statistical analysis. Following the presentation of the results, we provide a detailed discussion, interpreting the findings in relation to our research questions and existing literature, and highlighting the broader implication of our study.

Table 1 Level of Social media usage among MSU-SULU Senior High School Grade 12 Students

Time spent on social media	Frequency	Percent
Less than 1 hour	11	8.5
1-2 hours	38	29.2
3-4 hours	35	26.9
5-6 hours	18	13.8
More than 6 hours	28	21.5
Total	130	100.0

Table 1 presents the frequency count and percentage of students' time spent on social media, to determine their level of social media usage. As presented in the table a significant portion of MSU-SULU SHS Grade 12 students spend a considerable amount

of time on social media. The highest percentage of students (29.2%) spend 1-2 hours on social media daily. This indicates that a significant portion of students are engaged moderately on social media. A combined total of 26.9% of students spend between 3- 4 hours on social media, about 13.8% of students spend 5-6 hours and 21.5% spend more hours 6 hours on social media. The lowest percentage is 8.5% of students spend less than 1 hour on social media.

The results suggest that there is a moderate level of social media usage among MSU-SULU Senior High School Grade 12 students.

The findings in this table are related to the study of Tezci, & İçen, (2017), in which they have discovered that, Students spend between 1-3 hours daily on social media.

Table 2 Level of Environmental awareness among MSU-SULU Senior High School Grade 12 Students

Scale	Interpretation	Frequency	Percent
5	Very High level of environmental awareness	11	8.5
4	High level of environmental awareness	32	24.6
3	Moderate level of environmental awareness	52	40.0
2	Low level of environmental awareness	32	24.6
1	Very low level of environmental awareness	3	2.3
Total		130	100.0

Table 2 displays the frequency counts and percent of the level of student environmental awareness, measured by rating them in a scale 1 to 5, where 1 means low level of environmental awareness and 5 means high level of environmental awareness. As shown in the table large group of students (40%) rated their environmental awareness as 3/5, which indicates a moderate level of environmental awareness. Those who rated

their environmental awareness as 2/5 or low level of environmental awareness have the same outcome as those students who rated 4/5 or high level of environmental awareness, with a frequency count of 32 and a percentage of 24.6%. Additionally, the lowest frequency count and percentage are 5/5 or very high level of environmental awareness, which has a percentage of 8.5%, and the very low level of environmental awareness or 1/5 has a percentage of 2.3%.

The result indicates that MSU-SULU Senior High School Grade 12 students have a moderate level of environmental awareness. This means that the students have a concern about environmental issues and basic understanding about the issue, but their knowledge is not very deep and consistent.

This result is aligned with the study of Punzalan et al., (2019), according to his study Senior High School students in the Philippines exhibited a good to moderate level of environmental awareness.

Table 3 Social media usage increases environmental awareness

Choices	Frequency	Percent
Yes	106	81.5
No	24	18.5
Total	130	100.0

Table 3 presents the frequency counts and percentage of students who agreed and disagreed that social media usage increases their environmental awareness. As presented in the table 81.5% answer Yes or agreed that social media usage increases their environmental awareness, while 18.5% answers No or disagree that social media usage increases their environmental awareness.

The result suggested that 81.5% of students believe that social media usage increases their environmental awareness, while 18.5% do not think so.

This finding is related to the study of Thanya & Chandramohan (2023), in which the findings of their study indicate that social media is effective in promoting pro-environmental behavior and it also helps to understand the threats of environmental issues, especially climate change.

Table 4 Specific social media platform effective for increasing environmental awareness

Platforms	Frequency (Selected)	Percent
Facebook	80	61.5
TikTok	39	30.0
Instagram	10	7.7

YouTube	31	23.8
Twitter	6	4.6
Snapchat	1	0.8

Table 4 displays the social media platforms that are selected to be the most effective social media platform for environmental awareness. As shown in the table, **Facebook is the most effective** platform for increasing environmental awareness, with a significant lead over the others at 61.5%. This suggests that Facebook's broad reach, diverse content formats, and active user engagement make it the most preferred platform for environmental campaigns as chosen by the grade 12 students of MSU-SULU S.Y 2024-2025. **TikTok** ranks second with 30%, highlighting its growing influence, particularly through short form, engaging videos that appeal to younger audiences. **YouTube**, in third place (23%), is also a valuable tool for spreading awareness, likely due to its ability to host in-depth, educational content.

Platforms like **Instagram (7.7%)**, **Twitter (4.6%)**, and **Snapchat (0.8%)** are less effective for environmental awareness, possibly due to their format limitations, lower engagement with environmental content, or smaller reach in this context.

This result suggests that environmental campaigns should prioritize **Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube** to maximize reach and impact on environmental awareness.

The result in this table is aligned with the study of (Ozdemir & Alkabbanie, 2017), social media exerts a tremendous impact on molding environmental impressions, especially among the youth, owing to its accessibility, interaction, and visual appeal. Their analysis stressed that ads disseminated through popular platforms like Facebook and YouTube were more likely to generate environmental awareness and behavioral change than traditional techniques. To build on this, the present research indicates that to optimize reach and engagement, environmental initiatives should give priority to Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube. These platforms increase the overall efficacy of environmental message by providing wide access as well as dynamic and shareable content styles that appeal to younger, digitally native audiences.

Table 5.1 Significant relationship between social media usage and Environmental awareness among MSU-SULU Senior High School Grade 12 Students

Variable	N	M	SD	1	2
Social media usage	130	3.11	1.277	-	-
Environmental awareness	130	3.12	0.957	-	.177*

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

A Spearman's rho correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between social media usage and environmental awareness among a sample of 130 respondents. Descriptive statistics for the variable indicated that respondents reported an

average social media usage level (M = 3.11, SD = 1. 277) and an average environmental awareness level (M = 3.12, SD = 0.957).

The analysis revealed a **weak positive correlation (r = .177, p = 0.044, 2-tailed < p 0.05)**. This statistically significant relationship suggests that individuals who spend more time on social media tend to have slightly higher levels of environmental awareness. Although the correlation is weak, it indicates that social media usage may play a minor role in influencing or reflecting environmental awareness. However, other factors beyond social media likely contribute to environmental awareness.

This result is aligned with the study of Alsaad et al., (2023), in their study they found that, user engagements on social media is likely to involve caring and the responsibility ascription to protect the environment, which subsequently strengthens social media user’s intention to behave pro- environmentally.

Table 5.2 Significant relationship between social media usage and Environmental awareness using Descriptive frequency analysis

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Social media increase my awareness about environmental issue.	4.11	.750	Agree
2. Social media helps me understand the importance of environmental protection.	3.98	.787	Agree
3. I find it easy to use social media for gaining environmental knowledge.	3.97	.844	Agree
4. I often participate on environmental friendly content/post on social media.	3.13	1.045	Neutral
5. Videos about climate change helps me understand about environmental issues.	3.97	.806	Agree
6. I pay attention on environmental awareness content/post on social media.	3.75	.845	Agree
7. I find social media as reliable source of information for increasing environmental awareness.	3.74	.894	Agree
8. I like watching videos/post/content about our environment.	3.74	.911	Agree
9. Social media provides practical solutions to address environmental issue.	3.56	.854	Agree
10. I get motivated to take action in (e.g, recycling, reducing waste) because of social media.	3.68	.863	Agree
Grand Mean	3.76	.859	Agree

Legend: 4.20-5.00 (Strongly Agree); 3.40-4.19 (Agree); 2.60-3.39 (Neutral); 1.80-2.59 (Disagree); 1.00-1.79 (Strongly Disagree).

Table 5.2 illustrates the relationship between social media usage towards environmental awareness. As can be shown in the table presented, the grand mean resulted in 3.76, which shows that the students agreed with the statements implemented in the table. This means that there's a significant relationship between social media usage and environmental awareness wherein they have a favorable way of thinking and behavior towards it. The respondents agreed with the following statements. The students admit that social media increases their awareness about environmental issues, helps them understand the importance of environmental protection, and gets easy for gaining environmental knowledge with a total mean of 4.02.

However, the students show neutral that they often participate on environmental friendly content/post on social media with a total mean of 3.13. This suggests that while students are exposed to environmentally friendly content on social media, their engagement tends to be more passive than active.

The result is aligned with the study of Mallick (2019), in which he found that people nowadays are using social media to support environmental campaigns and to connect people locally and globally on minor to major environmental issues. It also provides ordinary people with the ability to track the quality of the climate around them and share this data with others.

Conclusions

The study has been conducted, and the results showed that there is a significant relationship between social media usage and environmental awareness among MSU-SULU Senior High School Grade 12 students. While majority of the students demonstrate a moderate level of social media usage and moderate level of environmental awareness. The findings indicate a weak but statistically significant positive correlation between social media usage and environmental awareness, suggesting that increased social media engagement might be associated with slightly heightened levels of environmental awareness. However, other factors likely play a more significant role in shaping environmental awareness of students. Furthermore, Facebook emerged as the most effective platform for environmental awareness campaigns followed by TikTok and YouTube, maybe due to their extensive reach and diverse content formats.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were based on the previous section of the study.

1. **For the school administrators**, School administrator should provide a curriculum that is easy for the students to understand, and follow will be convenient to monitor and evaluate the impact of social media on environmental awareness and regularly assess the effectiveness of social media-based environmental awareness initiatives and make data-driven decisions to improve their impact.
2. **For Teachers**, Teachers should incorporate environmental issues and sustainability into lesson plans to raise awareness and promote critical thinking and encourage them to initiate activities that relate on environmental issues and promote environmental awareness and sustainability.

3. **For Students**, Students should utilize social media platforms to stay informed about environmental issues, share eco-friendly practices, participate in online discussions and turn their environmental awareness into action.

4. **For future researchers**, may the problems and findings of this study serve as a guide for them to widen their perspective on how social media increases environmental awareness and how it significantly affects the students' perspectives towards environmental issues and identify strategies to promote sustainable practices. We also encourage them to explore the difference of environmental awareness based on strand and gender.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the researchers were committed to upholding the ethical standards. The researchers seek consent from all respondents, that they understand the study's purpose, and their right to withdraw at any time. The researchers protect the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents by using anonymized data and encrypted storage techniques. Respondents have rights, whether they give their names or not. Researchers respected privacy and the rights of the respondents. This research was carried out in an ethical way.

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